

LEVEL OF EMPLOYEE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY AND HEALTH IN CENTRAL KALIMANTAN PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

Occupational safety and health (OHS) is one of the important aspects of human resource management. Protection efforts aimed at ensuring that employees and others at work are always safe and healthy. Maintenance and improvement of the physical, mental, and social health of the workforce. Creating a safe, healthy, free workplace from environmental pollution, so that it can reduce and/or be free from occupational accidents and occupational diseases. Increase work productivity, reduce accident rates, and create a conducive work environment.

Keywords: Occupational Safety, Occupational Health and Employees

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A. INTRODUCTION

Human resources play an important role in the success of an organization, because humans are a living asset that needs special attention. The fact that people as the main asset in an organization should receive serious attention and be managed as best as possible. This is intended so that the human resources owned are able to make an optimal contribution in efforts to achieve organizational goals. In this human resource management, management is needed that is able to manage resources systematically, planned, and efficiently. The employees that the organization expects are of course employees who can work productively, namely those who are able to produce optimal work productivity as planned. Productivity is the main indicator of an organization's progress.

Organizations strive to increase the productivity of all their employees in order to be able to compete with other organizations because they can produce a good or service in a more efficient way. In addition to employee work productivity, there is also one thing that must be a concern, namely occupational safety and health. Occupational safety and health is one of the maintenance programs that should be in the organization. Occupational safety is safety related to human work activities both in industry, manufacturing and construction, which involves machinery, equipment, material handling, steam aircraft, pressure vessels, raw material work tools and their processing processes, workplace foundations and their environment and ways of doing work, as well as the service industry, which involves building cleaning equipment, transportation facilities, and others. Occupational health in the organization is a specialization in health science and its practice by conducting an assessment of the factors that cause disease in the work environment and the company through measurements whose results are used for the basis of corrective action and if necessary prevention to employees.

In the local government environment, it is not customary to enforce Occupational Safety and Health (K3) both in the form of policies and employees, because K3 is synonymous with private companies or state-owned enterprises engaged in construction, mining, and oil drilling as well as companies engaged in plantations and forestry. Each regional apparatus organization (OPD) should form an Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee (P2K3) which has the task of providing advice and consideration, whether requested or not, to OPDs regarding occupational safety and health issues.

Meanwhile, occupational safety and health should belong to everyone who is active with work, both those who are at low to high risk of occupational accidents. Work accidents start from the moment we leave from home to work and return home.

In every job, there is always a risk *of failures* in every work process/activity, whether it is due to imperfect planning, less careful implementation, or unintentional consequences such as weather conditions, natural disasters and so on. One of the occupational risks that occur is the existence of work accidents. When a work accident occurs, no matter how small, it will result in a loss effect, therefore as early as possible and as early as possible, accidents/potential work accidents must be prevented/eliminated, or at least the impact must be reduced.

As a researcher and at the same time as an expert on occupational safety and health (General K3 Expert) sees that occupational safety and health can be managed and prevented by identifying every problem that arises that can have a negative impact on safety and health for employees, until now there has been no effort to prevent risks that occur, so it is necessary to conduct an analysis of the level of occupational safety and health of employees in Central Kalimantan Province as efforts to prevent early risks to occupational safety and health for employees.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Occupational Safety

According to Sri Rejeki (2016:14) occupational safety is safety related to machinery, aircraft, work tools, materials and processing processes, the foundation of the workplace and its environment as well as ways of doing work. Occupational safety has the following properties:

- a. The target is the work environment;
- b. It is technical.

The term occupational safety and health varies, some call it *company hygiene and occupational health (hyperkes)* and some are simply abbreviated as *K3*, and in foreign terms it is known as occupational safety and health.

According to Widodo (2015:240) occupational safety is a form of circumstance that avoids mistakes and damage to work carried out by workers/employees.

According to Bennet N.B Silalahi and Rumondang (Widodo:2015:8), safety is an effort to prevent any unsafe deeds or conditions that can result in accidents.

2. Occupational health

According to Wirawan (2015:543) stated that occupational health is the application of health science or medicine in the field of employment which aims to prevent diseases arising from work and maintain and improve the health of workers/laborers to improve their performance.

Hartatik (2014:315) stated that "occupational health is a health condition that aims for workers to obtain the highest degree of health, both physical, spiritual, and social, with efforts to prevent and treat diseases or health disorders caused by work and work environment as well as general diseases".

Meanwhile, according to Prabu Mangkunegara (2001), the definition of occupational health is a condition free from physical, mental, emotional or pain disorders caused by the work environment. Health in the scope of occupational safety and health is not only defined as a state of being free from disease.

3. Work Accidents

According to Gunawan and Waluyo (2015:8), a work accident is an unplanned and unexpected event that can disrupt the production/operation process, damage property/assets, injure humans or damage the environment.

According to Ridley (2008:113) accidents do not occur, but are caused by weaknesses on the part of the employer, workers, or both. The consequences can cause trauma for both. For workers, injuries can affect their personal, family, and quality of life, while for employers, it is in the form of production losses, wasted time for investigations, and worst of all, the cost of legal proceedings

According to Wikipedia (February 19, 2020) there are at least 3 dominant factors that cause accidents on the road, namely human error, vehicle and environmental technicalities or road facilities.

4. Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee (P2K3)

In accordance with the Regulation of the Minister of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia Number: Per.04/Men/1987 concerning the Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee and the Procedure for the Appointment of Occupational Safety Experts Article 1 point d reads that the Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee, hereinafter referred to as P2K3, is an auxiliary body in the workplace which is a forum for cooperation between employers and workers to develop cooperation, mutual understanding and effective participation in the implementation of safety and health work.

Article 2 (1) Every workplace with certain criteria employers or administrators are obliged to form P2K3. (2) The workplace referred to in paragraph (1) is: a. a workplace where an employer or manager employs 100 or more people; b. workplaces where employers or administrators employ less than 100 people, but use materials, processes and installations that have a high risk of explosion, fire, poisoning and radioactive irradiation. Article 3 (1) The membership of P2K3 consists of elements of entrepreneurs and workers whose composition consists of the Chairman, Secretary and Members. (2) The P2K3 Secretary is an Occupational Safety expert from the company concerned. (3)

P2K3 is determined by the Minister or Official appointed by him at the proposal of the businessman or administrator concerned. Article 4 (1) P2K3 has the task of providing advice and consideration, whether requested or not, to employers or administrators regarding occupational safety and health issues.

5. Training, Curriculum and Modules

Training quoted from the id.wikipedia.org page is a short-term educational process using systematic and organized procedures, so that operational employees learn knowledge of engineering and expertise for a specific purpose.

The curriculum quoted from the id.wikipedia.org page is a set of subjects and educational programs provided by an [educational](#) institution that contains lesson plans that will be given to lesson participants in a period of [education level](#). The preparation of this subject set is adjusted to the circumstances and [abilities](#) of each level of education in the implementation of the education and the needs of employment. The length of time in one curriculum is usually adjusted to the purpose and objectives of the education system implemented. This curriculum is intended to be able to direct education towards the intended direction and goals in learning activities as a whole.

The training module quoted from <http://jurnal.ustjogja.ac.id> is one of the learning media that can be used as a medium for transforming knowledge, skills, and work attitudes to trainees to achieve certain competencies based on programs that refer to the Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI).

6. Official

Law Number 20 of 2023 concerning the State Civil Apparatus (ASN), in this law which means:

- a. State Civil Apparatus, hereinafter abbreviated as ASN, is a profession for civil servants and government employees with employment agreements who work in government agencies.
- b. State Civil Apparatus Employees, hereinafter referred to as ASN employees, are Civil Servants and government employees with work agreements appointed by personnel supervisory officials and assigned to other state duties and are paid based on laws and regulations.
- c. Civil Servants, hereinafter abbreviated as PNS, are Indonesian citizens who meet certain requirements, appointed as ASN employees on a permanent basis by personnel coaching officials to occupy government positions
- d. Government employees with a work agreement, hereinafter abbreviated as PPPK, are Indonesian citizens who meet certain conditions, who are appointed based on a work agreement for a certain period of time in order to carry out government duties.

According to the Great Dictionary of Indonesian, an employee is a person who works for the government, or a private company.

C. RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, the researcher uses a qualitative research approach. The reasons for the researcher to use this qualitative research approach are:

1. It is carried out under natural conditions. In conducting research, researchers go directly to the source of research as a key instrument. The natural condition in question is the condition as it is, the researcher does not carry out treatments that can affect the scientificity of the object being studied.

2. The data collected is made up of words and pictures, so that it does not press on numbers. The data collected after analysis is then described, so that it is easy for others to understand.
3. Focus on research that is process-based, such as interaction between people in a community, the process of carrying out work, and the development of a phenomenon.
4. Researchers analyze data based on data obtained from the field repeatedly, analyzed so that it will produce findings that can be compiled in a certain theme.
5. It emphasizes to understand the meaning in depth of a phenomenon, the meaning that is the result of the interpretation of a visible data.

Research site

This research was carried out by the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government

D. RESULTS

Based on data collected from 41 (forty-one) heads of agencies, heads of agencies, assistants, expert staff in the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government who were taken as respondents,

From the results of the interview directly and using *the google form* , the following results were obtained:

1. From the results mentioned above, 97.6% or 40 regional apparatus organizations do not have K3 experts, only 2.4% or 1 OPD has K3 experts
2. There are 7.3% or 3 OPDs that have health clinics and 92.7% or 38 do not have health clinics.
3. All regional or 100% water hydrant devices
4. All regional apparatus has a light or 100% fire extinguisher with the number of units ranging from 1 to 20 units per OPD, but not all OPDs understand how to use the existing fire extinguishers, which is 87.6% or 36 OPDs. Although fire extinguishers are available, simulations of how to use them have never been carried out, there have also been fires, this can be seen from the data collected, namely 92.7% or 38 OPDs, while only 7.3% or 3 OPDs have ever conducted simulations. As a result of the non-optimal use of fire extinguishers, there have been light to severe fires in 10 OPDs caused by electrical short circuits.
5. All regional devices have an assembly point or 100%
6. The availability of signs in several OPDs is at least 65.9% or 27 OPDs, there are 34.1% or 14 OPDs.
7. All OPDs have good lighting and humidity of temperature and air, a clean environment and have an ergonomic workspace.
8. Several employees have experienced minor to severe accidents caused by the lack of proper vehicles they use and the lack of employee understanding of traffic signs.
9. OPDs that do not have routine scheduling of vehicle maintenance 92.7% or 38 OPDs
10. Of the 41 OPDs, only 12 OPDs routinely carry out health checks for employees, while 70.7% or 29 OPDs do not schedule health checks for their employees.
11. Results of interviews with the main informant

From the results of the interview with the main informant who is the head of the Kalimantan Provincial Human Resources Development Agency as well as the policy maker of Occupational Safety and Health training, from the results of the interview, the results are presented in the following table:

Table 4.1 Results of interviews with main informants

Question	Main Informant's Answer
What are the concrete steps as a core decision-maker to support employee safety in the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government?	1. Optimizing existing OSH expert tasks 2. Will form an Occupational Health Safety Advisory Committee (P2K3)
What infrastructure facilities will be provided for employee work safety	Will cooperate with the vehicle maintenance unit in the context of vehicle maintenance owned by employees
What is done to increase employee occupational safety awareness	1. Competency test for prospective K3 Experts 2. Forming a team to create curriculum and modules related to K3 3. Will organize K3 training for employees
Looking at the obstacles and causes of work accidents that are not only internal to BPSDM but also related to other parties, what will be done in the future?	Conducting MoU and Cooperation with related agencies (Manpower Service, Fire Department, Transportation Service, Police and other related agencies).

E. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion in this study, the following results can be concluded:

- a. From the results mentioned above, 97.6% or 40 regional apparatus organizations do not have K3 experts, only 2.4% or 1 OPD has K3 experts.
- b. There are 7.3% or 3 OPDs that have health clinics and 92.7% or 38 do not have health clinics.
- c. All regional or 100% devices have water hydrants.
- d. All regional apparatus has a light or 100% fire extinguisher with the number of units ranging from 1 to 20 units per OPD, but not all OPDs understand how to use the existing fire extinguishers, which is 87.6% or 36 OPDs. Although fire extinguishers are available, simulations of how to use them have never been carried out, there have also been fires, this can be seen from the data collected, namely 92.7% or 38 OPDs, while only 7.3% or 3 OPDs have ever conducted simulations. As a result of the non-optimal use of fire extinguishers, there have been light to severe fires in 10 OPDs caused by electrical short circuits.
- e. All regional devices have an assembly point or 100%
- f. The availability of signs in several OPDs is at least 65.9% or 27 OPDs, there are 34.1% or 14 OPDs.
- g. All OPDs have good lighting and humidity of temperature and air, a clean environment and have an ergonomic workspace.
- h. Several employees have experienced minor to severe accidents caused by the lack of proper vehicles they use and the lack of employee understanding of traffic signs.

- i. OPDs that do not have routine scheduling of vehicle maintenance 92.7% or 38 OPDs
- j. Of the 41 OPDs, only 12 OPDs routinely carry out health checks for employees, while 70.7% or 29 OPDs do not schedule health checks for their employees.

2. Recommendations

From the results of this study, it is recommended for the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government as follows:

- a. Design curriculum and training modules related to employee occupational safety and health by considering the following aspects:
 - a. Institutional strengthening;
 - b. Work safety;
 - c. Work accidents;
 - d. Work environment
 - e. Introduction of traffic signs and K3
 - f. Multi-stakeholder cooperation.
- b. So that every regional apparatus organization has a General K3 Expert
- c. So that each regional apparatus organization has its own health clinic.
- d. Conduct periodic employee health checks.
- e. Organizing occupational safety and health training for employees:
- f. Optimizing the duties of Occupational Safety and Health Experts (K3) within the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government.
- g. The establishment of the Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee (P2K3) which has the task of providing advice and consideration, whether requested or not, to the leadership regarding employee occupational safety and health issues.
- h. Cooperation with two-wheeled and four-wheeled motor vehicle maintenance units in providing employee motor vehicle maintenance services;
- i. MoU with OPDs related to employee work safety such as the Manpower Service, Fire Department, Transportation Service, Police and other related agencies.

REFERENCE

- [1] Anita Dewi PS.2012. Fundamentals of Occupational Safety and Health. Jember: UNEJ Publishing Unit
- [2] Gunawan and Waluyo.2015. Risk Based Behavioral Safety builds togetherness to realize operational excellence. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama
- [3] Ike Racmawati Kusdyah.2008. Human Resource Management. Yogyakarta. ANDI
- [4] Indah Racmawati Siti Salami. 2019. Health and Safety of the Work Environment. Yogyakarta: Gajah Mada University Press
- [5] Juliansyah Noor.2015. Research Methodology of Definitions, Thesis, Dissertations and Scientific Works:Jakarta:Kencana Prenada Media Group
- [6] Rudi Suardi.2005. Occupational Safety and Health Management System. Jakarta:PPM
- [7] Ridley, Jhon.2008. Third Edition Occupational Health and Safety Overview. Jakarta. Erlangga
- [8] Sedarmayanti.2011.Human Resource Management, Bureaucratic Reform and Civil Servant Resource Management. Bandung. PT Refika Aditama
- [9] Sugiyono. 2020. Qualitative Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta
- [10] Soehatman Ramli: 2010.OHSAS 18001 Occupational Safety and Health Management System. Jakarta: Dian Rakyat
- [11] Widodo. 2015. Human Resource Development Management. Yogyakarta:Student Library
- [12] Sri Rejeki.2016. Occupational Health and Safety. Jakarta: Health HR Center
- [13] Wowo Sunaryo Kuswana.2017.Ergonomics and K3 Occupational Health and Safety.Bandung.PT Remaja Rosdakarya

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- [14] Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 1970 concerning Occupational Safety
- [15] Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 13 of 1970 concerning Manpower
- [16] Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2014 concerning the State Civil Apparatus
- [17] The Great Dictionary of Indonesian Online <http://kbbi.kemdikbud.go.id/> dated March 29, 2021.
- [18] <https://id.wikipedia.org> September 28, 2021
- [18] <http://jurnal.ustjogja.ac.id> September 28, 2021

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